

Numerical Library Eigensolver Performance on PRACE Tier-0 Systems

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Abstract

Parallel eigensolver operations are at the computational core of many large-scale scientific and engineering application codes. This project analyses parallel performance of established and newly developed parallel dense symmetric eigensolver numerical library routines on PRACE Tier-0 systems using real datasets from large-scale application codes. This whitepaper builds upon the research report 'Dense Linear Algebra Performance Analysis on the Fujitsu BX900 OPL Machine'[†] (from the same author) which can be found at: http://www.openpetascale.org/documents/2011_Dense_Linear_Algebra_Performance_Analysis_on_the_Fujitsu_BX900_OPL_Machine.pdf. This version of the report is updated with results from ScaLAPACK and with the recently released ELPA library routines on the PRACE Tier-0 machines CURIE and JUGENE.

1. Introduction

Eigenvalue and eigenvector computations arise in a wide range of scientific and engineering applications. For example, in quantum chemistry and atomic physics the computation of eigenvalues is often required to obtain electronic energy states. For large-scale complex systems in such areas, the eigensolve usually represents a huge computational challenge. Efficient eigensolver performance using the latest optimized algorithms that attempt to take full advantage of the underlying architecture is therefore of critical importance to many large-scale scientific application codes. The matrices used for benchmarking are representative Hartree-Fock datasets from the large-scale computational electronic structure application code CRYSTAL.

2. Recent Developments in Parallel Numerical Libraries

Several new numerical libraries for multi/many core platforms, such as PLASMA (Parallel Linear Software for Multicore Architectures) and MAGMA (Matrix Algebra on GPU and Multicore Architectures), are currently under development [1] [2]. These libraries are being developed as successors to ScaLAPACK (homogeneous distributed memory) [3] in order to exploit multi/many core and (heterogeneous shared/distributed) CPU / GPU architectures. Another new parallel library under development is SLEPc (Scalable Library for Eigenvalue Problem Computations) [4], which is an extension of the sparse linear solver package PETSc for sparse parallel eigensolvers [5]. At the time of writing both PLASMA and MAGMA are limited to linear solver routines (LU, Cholesky etc), with no symmetric standard eigensolver implementations (though these are apparently being planned) and SLEPc only addresses sparse eigensolvers.

There have recently been two notable software developments for parallel dense symmetric eigensolvers. Firstly, in May 2011 an initiative supported by the German government involving several research centres in Germany and IBM released the numerical library "Eigenvalue Solvers for Petaflop-Architectures" (ELPA) [6]. This library targets matrices from electronic structure calculations and introduces more efficient 'two-step' methods for the reduction stage and the back transformation stage [7]. At the time of writing, only an MPI version of the software has been released. However testing and development of a hybrid MPI / OpenMP version of the software is currently underway and hopefully this will be made available in the near future. Secondly, in November 2011 ScaLAPACK version 2.0 [8] was released which includes the first official versions of 'Multiple Relatively Robust Representations' algorithms for symmetric eigensolvers [9]. Algorithms based on this approach have been available in LAPACK for quite some time and beta versions of the routine PDSYEVH have been tested in previous reports [10] [11][12].

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[†] The Open Petascale Libraries Project, www.openpetascale.org: Advancing the development of software for the new generation of highly parallel computers.

Therefore, at the time of writing, the new numerical library routines of interest for parallel symmetric eigensolves are those from ScaLAPACK and ELPA and this report will focus on the performance of these routines.

3. Solving the Symmetric Eigenvalue Problem[‡]

Many high-end scientific application codes under development, including those tested here, involve the computation of the symmetric real or Hermitian eigenvalue problem. Computational chemists generally require all or a subset of the spectrum and its associated eigen-subspaces. For most applications the solution of the eigenproblem (i.e. diagonalization) is limited by available processing time and computer memory. A summary of methods for tackling the symmetric eigenvalue problem is given in [13]. It is also useful to give a brief overview here of the characteristics and computational properties of the specific methods analysed in this report.

3.1. Problem Definition

The Standard Eigenvalue Problem is described as

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} = \lambda \mathbf{x},$$

where \mathbf{A} is a matrix and λ is the eigenvalue corresponding to eigenvector \mathbf{x} .

The Generalized Eigenvalue Problem has a number of forms. The most common in scientific computing is

$$\mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} = \lambda \mathbf{B} \mathbf{x},$$

where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are matrices, and again λ is an eigenvalue corresponding to eigenvector \mathbf{x} . This generalized eigenvalue problem can always be reduced to the standard problem if matrix \mathbf{B} has an inverse.

As noted above in scientific applications, matrix \mathbf{A} is typically Hermitian, and this should be assumed from now in this report unless otherwise stated. For the generalized case it is also usual that matrix \mathbf{B} is Hermitian and positive definite. These two properties allow this form of the generalized eigenvalue problem to be readily reduced to the standard problem whilst retaining the Hermiticity of the matrix to be solved. Consequently we now focus of the standard Hermitian (or real symmetric, as all real symmetric matrices are Hermitian) problem.

The eigenvalues and eigenvectors of a Hermitian matrix have a number of useful properties than are summarized here:

1. The eigenvectors of a Hermitian matrix form a complete set, i.e. for an order n matrix there are exactly n distinct normalized eigenvectors
2. All the eigenvalues are real
3. For non-degenerate eigenvalues the corresponding eigenvectors are orthogonal
4. For degenerate eigenvalues the corresponding eigenvectors may always be chosen to be orthogonal. In scientific computing orthogonal eigenvectors are usually the most convenient choice.

3.2. Algorithms for Computing Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors

The solution to the real or hermitian dense symmetric eigensolver problem usually takes place via three main steps:

1. Reduction of the matrix to tri-diagonal form, typically using the Householder Reduction.
2. Solution of the real symmetric tri-diagonal eigenproblem via one of the following methods:
 - Bisection for the eigenvalues and inverse iteration for the eigenvectors,
 - QR algorithm,
 - Divide & Conquer method (D&C),
 - Multiple Relatively Robust Representations (MR³ algorithm).

[‡] The Technical Report "Using Scalable Eigensolvers on HPCx: Case Studies" [13] provides a good summary of the symmetric eigensolver problem and the algorithms used for its computation. We therefore think it is worthwhile to repeat much of this section here.

3. Back transformation to find the eigenvectors for the full problem from the eigenvectors of the tridiagonal problem.

Steps 1 and 3 are common to all the algorithms discussed here. For step 1., employing Householder transformations to reduce the original matrix to tridiagonal form costs about $4/3n^3$ operation. Back-transformation in Step 3 requires $2n^3$ operations. The cost of solving the tridiagonal eigenproblem in Step 2 varies from $O(n^2)$ to $O(kn^3)$ ($4 < k < 12$) according to the method used and the numerical characteristics of the matrix. Moreover, Steps 1 and 3 can exploit highly-optimised matrix-multiply operations whereas Step 2 cannot. Therefore the tridiagonal eigensolve usually represents the computational bottleneck in the solution of eigenproblems and it is this stage of the calculation that has received the most attention from developers of eigensolver algorithms. Four alternative approaches to the tridiagonal eigensolve are listed above and their parallel implementations are discussed in more detail in the next section.

3.3. Current Algorithms for Solving the Symmetric Tridiagonal Eigenproblem

3.3.1. Divide-and-Conquer Algorithm

The divide-and-conquer approach is based on a method described by Dhillon [14]. This approach divides the triangular matrix into two parts, solves the eigenproblem for each part recursively and then combines the solution to each sub-problem to give a solution to the original problem.

3.3.2. The Multiple Relatively Robust Representation Algorithm

MR³ is an approach developed recently by Dhillon et al [9]. This algorithm applies a shift σ to T near each cluster of eigenvalues and computes an LDLT factorization of $(T - \sigma I)$. A suitable choice of σ eliminates the need for costly re-orthogonalizations when the eigenvalues are tightly clustered. The method is based upon the property that small relative changes in entries of L and D cause small relative changes in each eigenvalue of T. The algorithm requires $O(nk)$ operations, where k is the number of eigenpairs to be found. This computational requirement is much lower than the other methods listed here. The MR³ algorithm also has the added advantage of requiring only $O(n)$ workspace, thereby increasing the maximum size of system that can be solved.

3.4. Numerical Library Routines for Solving the Standard Dense Symmetric Eigensolver Problem

3.4.1. The ScaLAPACK routine PDSYEVD

The ScaLAPACK routines PDSYEVD and PZHEEVD, released with library version 1.7 calculate all the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of a symmetric or Hermitian matrix using divide-and-conquer based methods. Previous performance analysis investigations have demonstrated that this approach scales well on large parallel machines [11] and its performance is often several times faster than the older ScaLAPACK routines PDSYEV and PDSYEVX. One drawback is the large amount of temporary workspace required (of order between $2n^3$ and $3n^3$).

3.4.2. The new ScaLAPACK routine PDSYEVR

The ScaLAPACK MRRR driver routine PDSYEVR includes the following routines for the three operations listed above:

1. Transform full matrix into tridiagonal form (PDSYNTRD)
2. Compute the eigenpairs of the tridiagonal matrix:
 - Compute root representations and root eigenvalues (DSTAGR2A)
 - Share eigenvalues between processors (DGEBS2D & DGEBR2D)
 - Compute representation tree and eigenvectors (DSTAGR2B, DLARRV)
3. Compute the back transformation (PDORMTR)

As with the PDSYEVX routine, PDSYEV is an expert ScaLAPACK driver, in that a user-defined subset of eigenvalues and/or eigenvectors can be computed. This is in contrast to the simple ScaLAPACK drivers PDSYEV and PDSYEV, where all the eigenvalues and/or eigenvectors are always computed. The implementation and features of the new implementation are discussed in detail in [10].

3.4.3. The new ELPA routines *solv_esp_real* & *solve_esp_real_2stage*

The ELPA software provides routines for two different approaches to optimizing eigensolver performance on Petaflop systems [6]. Firstly the ELPA 1 STAGE modules, including the routine *solve_esp_real* tested here, focus on reducing communication overheads and maximizing cache performance for existing standard ScaLAPACK routines (PDSYEV). ELPA 2 STAGE routines such as *solve_esp_real_2stage* add extra steps into the traditional three-step standard eigensolver approach outlined in the previous section. An intermediate banded representation of the matrix is formed during the reduction to tridiagonal form. Likewise an intermediate banded form is generated during the back transformation stage of the calculation. Both ELPA solvers can be directed to calculate a subset of eigenpairs if preferred by the user.

Optimized linear algebra kernels are provided as part of the standard ELPA download. The files are generic versions of optimized linear algebra kernels for use with the ELPA library. These can run on any platform but are optimized particularly for both the Power PC450 found on the IBM Blue Gene/P and the Intel SSE instruction set found on CURIE hardware. On CURIE it is advised that best performance is achieved with the Intel ifort compiler and compile flags -O3 -xSSE4.2.

4. Performance Results

4.1. Architectures, Environments and Libraries

4.1.1. JUGENE IBM Blue Gene/P

Hardware: Power PC 450, 32-bit, 850 MHz, 4-way SMP with 2GB with three-dimensional torus interconnect

Compilation / Runtime Environment:

module load scalapack/2.0.1 (or module load scalapack/2.0.1_450d for double hummer version)
SCK_LIBS = -L\$(SCALAPACK_LIB) -lscalapack -L\$(LAPACK_LIB) -llapack -L/bgsys/local/lib -lesslbg

4.1.2. TGCC CURIE (Phase 1) Bull Intel Westmere

Hardware: B510 Bullx nodes. Each node comprises 4 eight-core Intel® Nehalem processors (EX-X7560) 2.26 GHz, 128 GB. Infiniband QDR Full Fat Tree network.

Compilation / Runtime Environment:

MKL_SCA_LIBS = -L/usr/local/Intel_compilers/c/composer_xe_2011_sp1.7.256/mkl/lib/intel64 -lmkl_intel_lp64 -lmkl_sequential -lmkl_scalapack_lp64 -lmkl_core -lmkl_blacs_openmpi_lp64 -lm

4.2. Performance Tests

All performance analysis tests for this exercise measure strong scaling, i.e. performance is compared across a range of core counts using the same datasets with the same dimensions. This is the basis for most of the charts presented in this report. Observations regarding weak scaling properties can also be made, as some of the applications tested here provide several matrices with similar characteristics, but differing dimensions. Except where explicitly stated, all results refer to calculations involving the complete spectrum of eigenpairs. All results have been obtained on compute nodes fully occupied with tasks, i.e. the number of MPI tasks is equal to the number of physical cores reserved for the benchmark run.

4.2.1. Test Application Code: CRYSTAL

The CRYSTAL package performs ab initio calculations of the ground state energy, electronic wave function and properties of periodic systems. Development of the software has taken place jointly by the Theoretical Chemistry Group at the University of Torino and the Computational Materials Science Group at STFC Daresbury Laboratory (UK) [17]. The computation of the electronic structure is performed using either Hartree-Fock or Density Functional theory. In each case the fundamental approximation made is the expansion of the single particle wave functions as a linear combination of atom centred atomic orbitals (LCAO) based on Gaussian functions. The real symmetric standard eigensolve is required inside a Self-Consistent-Field (SCF) calculation in an iterative cycle as part of a Hartree-Fock DFT calculation. In practice the eigensolve is therefore often repeated many times per simulation, representing a significant portion of overall run-time.

Three different Hartree-Fock matrices were used for the tests with dimension 3888, 7194 and 20480 (CRY3888, CRY7194, CRY20480). All the systems are real and symmetric and contain some groups of closely clustered eigenvalues that normally can represent significant computational challenges for parallel solvers. For all the benchmarks described here, a full set of eigenpairs is calculated. These matrix characteristics are typical of electronic structure calculations as this pattern is consistent with the clustered energy levels in atomic configurations. In order to place these benchmarks in their proper context within the overall application, it should be noted that eigensolves of matrices with relatively modest dimensions (e.g. 3888, 7194) often have to be undertaken on relatively large core counts (e.g. 256+ cores) (i.e. runs with relatively low n/p ratios where n is the matrix dimension and p represents the number of cores) when undertaken within CRYSTAL. This is because other parts of the computation, such as the integral calculation, are expensive but their parallel performance tends to scale better and therefore these large core counts are necessary.

4.2.2. Parallel Performance Results from JUGENE

Fig. 1. ScaLAPACK and ELPA Eigensolver Performance Comparison on JUGENE IBM BG/P for Matrix CRY3888

Fig. 2. ScaLAPACK and ELPA Eigensolver Performance Comparison on JUGENE IBM BG/P for Matrix CRY7194

Fig. 3. ScaLAPACK and ELPA Eigensolver Performance Comparison on JUGENE IBM BG/P for Matrix CRY20480

The performance results from JUGENE shown in Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show that, for these datasets, the new ELPA routines solve_evp_real and solve_evp_real_2stage significantly out-perform the ScaLAPACK eigensolvers PDSYEVD and PDSYEVR. The performance improvements are particularly noticeable where strong scaling is being tested in the extreme e.g. a 1024 core eigensolve of the CRY3888 matrix in Fig. 1. Here, no performance gains are obtained from runs involving core counts beyond 256 for the ScaLAPACK solvers, but scaling continues out to 1024 cores for both ELPA routines. For CRY3888 the performance ratio between ELPA 1 STAGE and PDSYEVD at 256 cores is around 2, rising to 3.4 on 1024 cores. Similarly for CRY7194 in Fig. 2, the improvement from the ELPA routines is largest at the higher core counts. Here the ratio is 3.7 on 2048 cores for ELPA 1 STAGE. The scalability curves for ELPA and ScaLAPACK show similar patterns for the large CRY20480

case in Fig. 3, where once again ELPA outperforms ScaLAPACK by a factor of two to three for higher core counts. It is noted that the parallel performance achieved from the higher core counts in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 diminishes for the PDSYEVVR routine. It is believed that this behaviour is associated with problems in distributing the representation tree when the number of MPI tasks becomes very large [10]. The ELPA 1 STAGE solver consistently outperforms the ELPA 2 STAGE solver for the two smaller cases, indicating that overhead improvements and cache optimizations are generally more important factors in improving performance for smaller matrices than the rewriting of the algorithm to a two stage procedure. However the scaling of ELPA 2 STAGE is approximately equal to ELPA 1 STAGE in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, and it is shown that ELPA2 performance results almost equal the scalability and time taken for ELPA 1 STAGE on larger core counts for the relatively large case in Fig. 3.

4.2.3. Parallel Performance Results from CURIE

Fig. 4. ScaLAPACK and ELPA Eigensolver Performance Comparisons on CURIE Bull Phase 1 System for Matrix CRY3888

Fig. 5. ScaLAPACK and ELPA Eigensolver Performance Comparisons on CURIE Bull Phase 1 System for Matrix CRY7194

Fig. 6. ScaLAPACK and ELPA Eigensolver Performance Comparisons on CURIE Bull Phase 1 System for Matrix CRY20480

Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 present performance results for ScaLAPACK and ELPA eigensolvers on the CEA CURIE PRACE system. Once again the ELPA 1 STAGE routines perform best for the small and medium sized datasets. However on the large CRY20480 matrix the ELPA 2 STAGE approach was yielding significant improvements, both in speed and scalability. The scalability could not be tested further on CURIE as a job size of 1024 cores is currently the largest allowed for this PRACE work package allocation. The ELPA routines significantly outperform the existing ScaLAPACK divide-and-conquer and MRRR routines. The performance ratio between the best ELPA solver and best ScaLAPACK solver is 1.98 on 128 cores for CRY3888, 1.8 on 256 cores for CRY7194 and 2.36 on 1024 cores for CRY20480.

4.2.4. Comparison of JUGENE and CURIE Performance Results

Fig. 7. PDSYEVD and ELPA 1 STAGE Timings for CRY7194 on JUGENE and CURIE Phase 1

Fig. 7 compares time to solution for the solvers investigated on the CURIE (Phase 1) and JUGENE platforms for the CRY7194 dataset. For the PDSYEVD routine, time to solution on 32 cores of CURIE is 4.52 faster than the time taken on the same number of cores on JUGENE. On 256 cores this ratio has reduced to 2.94. For the ELPA 1 STAGE routine the performance of CURIE is 3.31 times faster on 32 cores and 3.04 times faster on 256 cores. These ratios are generally comparable to those measured in benchmarks from other application codes and routines (e.g. FFTs) and broadly reflect the relative clock speeds of the different CPUs from CURIE and JUGENE.

5. Summary

Only a small amount of resources (1.5 man months) were available for this analysis of dense symmetric eigensolvers in PRACE. It was therefore not possible to do a comprehensive study of all available eigensolver routines for datasets from a wide range of applications. However the Hartree-Fock datasets used are representative of those formed in many electronic structure application codes (e.g. GPAW, LSDALTON, Quantum Espresso) and, at least until the release of comparable routines in the MAGMA and PLASMA libraries, ScaLAPACK and ELPA are currently the best options for numerical library-based eigen-solutions on Tier-0 systems such as CURIE and JUGENE.

The performance results from the new ELPA software package are particularly impressive. Not only are the routines significantly faster than their ScaLAPACK counterparts, but also the scalability is better throughout (however it should be noted that PDSYEVVR is aimed at cases where only a subset of eigenpairs is required). It is often the case in Hartree-Fock computational cycles that a matrix of relatively modest dimension (e.g. 3888) needs to be solved many times over using a large number of cores. The reason being that the number of cores used is often determined by the demands of the integral calculation (which scales better) rather than the eigensolve. Given the importance of eigensolver performance to many physics and chemistry application codes, the two-fold to three-fold advantage in performance rendered by ELPA over ScaLAPACK, measured on both JUGENE and CURIE for a range of problem sizes, is likely to impact overall application performance significantly. Moreover, ELPA is also designed to be a 'drop-in' substitute for ScaLAPACK – e.g. it uses the same block-cyclic data distribution – and therefore applying it to application codes with existing ScaLAPACK interfaces should be straightforward. At this stage it is not clear which of the two ELPA eigensolvers performs best, though a pattern evident in these benchmarks is that the one-stage solution performs best on smaller datasets whilst the two-stage approach scales better and is more efficient on larger test cases.

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